

TENSILE PROPERTIES OF CARBON NANOTUBES GRAFTED HIGH STRENGTH PAN-BASED CARBON FIBERS

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1 Introduction

Carbon fibers are widely used as a reinforcement in composite materials because of their high specific strength and modulus. Such composites have become a dominant material in the aerospace, automotive and sporting goods industries [1,2]. Current trends toward the development of carbon fibers have been driven in two directions; ultrahigh tensile strength fiber with a fairly high strain to failure (~2%), and ultrahigh modulus fiber with high thermal conductivity. Today, a number of ultrahigh strength PAN-based (more than 6 GPa), and ultrahigh modulus pitch-based (more than 900 GPa) carbon fibers have been commercially available. Recently, the tensile, flexural properties and Weibull modulus of ultrahigh strength PAN-based, ultrahigh modulus pitch-based and high ductility pitch-based single carbon fibers were characterized by Naito et al [3,4].

The grafting of carbon nanotubes (CNTs) on carbon fibers has been reported in the literature [5,6]. CNTs grafted carbon fibers offer the opportunity to add the potential benefits of nanoscale reinforcement to well-established fibrous composites to create multiscale hybrid micro-nano composites [6]. However, the effect of grafting CNTs on the mechanical properties of carbon fiber has not been evaluated. Naito et al. reported that the grafting of CNTs improves the tensile strength and Weibull modulus of ultrahigh strength PAN-based and ultrahigh modulus pitch-based carbon fibers [7].

In the present work, the tensile tests of single filaments at several gauge length for CNTs grafted ultrahigh strength PAN-based carbon fiber were performed. The effects of gauge length on tensile

strength and Weibull modulus of CNTs grafted carbon fiber were evaluated.

2 Experimental

2.1 Materials

Carbon fiber used in this study was an ultrahigh tensile strength PAN-based (T1000GB) carbon fiber. The T1000GB PAN-based carbon fiber was supplied from Toray Industries, Inc.

To grow CNTs on the carbon fiber, an $\text{Fe}(\text{C}_5\text{H}_5)_2$ (ferrocene) catalyst was applied to the T1000GB fiber bundle using thermal chemical vapor deposition (CVD) in vacuum. Experimental details on the CNTs synthesis technique can be found elsewhere [5]. Prior to the application of the catalyst, the carbon fiber bundle was heat treated at 750 °C for an hour in vacuum to remove the sizing. The growth temperature and time for CNTs deposition were selected as 750 °C for 900 sec.

2.2 Tensile Test

A single filament was selected from carbon fiber bundle and cut perpendicular to the fiber axis by a razor blade. Tensile tests of single carbon fibers were performed using a universal testing machine (Shimadzu, Table top type tester EZ-Test) with a load cell of 10 N. The tensile specimen was prepared by fixing the filament on a paper holder with an instant cyanoacrylate adhesive, as reported elsewhere [8]. The holder was cut into two parts before testing. The gauge length, L of 1, 5 and 25 mm, and crosshead speed of 0.5 mm/min were applied. All tests were conducted under laboratory conditions at room temperature (23 ± 3 °C) and

50±5 % relative humidity. Twenty specimens were tested for all carbon fibers.

3 Results and Discussions

3.1 Grafting CNTs on the fiber

Fig.1 shows the SEM micrograph of surface view for the as-received T1000GB PAN-based carbon fiber filament.

Fig.1. SEM micrograph of the surface view for as-received T1000GB PAN-based carbon fiber.

The as-received T1000GB PAN-based carbon fiber has a comparatively smooth surface.

Fig.2 shows the SEM micrograph of CNTs grown on the T1000GB PAN-based carbon fiber filament.

(a) low magnification.

(b) high magnification.

Fig.2. SEM micrograph of CNTs grown on T1000GB PAN-based carbon fiber.

The CNTs can be grafted nearly perpendicular to the fiber surfaces, and grown uniformly and densely on the T1000GB fiber.

3.2 Effect of gauge length on tensile strength

The tensile strength, σ_f was calculated using:

$$\sigma_f = \frac{P_{max}}{\left(\frac{\pi d_f^2}{4}\right)} \quad (1)$$

where P_{max} and d_f are the maximum fracture load and the diameter of the single carbon fiber.

The average tensile strengths ($\sigma_{f,ave}$) at various gauge length are summarized in Table 1 and the relation between the enhancing ratio, $\left(\frac{\sigma_{f,ave (CNTs-grafted)} - \sigma_{f,ave (as-received)}}{\sigma_{f,ave (as-received)}} * 100\right)$ and the gauge length, L ranging from 1 to 25 mm was shown in Fig.3.

These results show that the average tensile strength of CNTs grown on ultrahigh strength T1000GB fiber at gauge length of 1, 5 and 25 mm is 8.97 ± 0.80 , 8.23 ± 0.84 and 6.73 ± 1.01 GPa, which is 0, 7 and 18 % higher than that in the as-received state (8.98 ± 0.80 , 7.71 ± 0.88 and 5.69 ± 1.02 GPa) [3,7]. Evidently, the grafting of CNTs improved the average tensile strength of PAN-based carbon fibers at gauge length of 5 and 25 mm. However, the average tensile strength of CNTs grafted PAN-based carbon fibers at gauge length of 1 mm is almost identical to that in the as-received state.

Table 1. Mechanical properties of ultrahigh strength PAN-based (T1000GB) carbon fibers.

Fiber	Gauge length L (mm)	T1000GB	
		As- received	CNTs- grafted
Filaments ^a (Count)		12000	---
Yield (Tex) ^a (g/1000m)		485	---
Density ^a ρ (g/cm ³)		1.80	---
	1	8.98 (0.80)	8.97 (0.80)
Average tensile strength σ_{ave} (GPa)	5	7.71 (0.88)	8.23 (0.84)
	25	5.69 ^b (1.02)	6.73 ^c (1.01)

Fig.3. Relation between the enhancing ratio and the gauge length.

3.3 Effect of gauge length on Weibull modulus

There is an appreciable scattering of tensile strength for the carbon fibers. The statistical distribution of fiber strengths is usually described by means of the Weibull equation [9]. The two-parameter Weibull distribution is given by

$$P_F = 1 - \exp\left[-\frac{L}{L_0}\left(\frac{\sigma_f}{\sigma_0}\right)^{m_f}\right] \quad (2)$$

where P_F is the cumulative probability of failure of a carbon fiber of length L at applied tensile strength σ_f , m_f is the Weibull modulus (Weibull shape parameter) of the carbon fiber, σ_0 a Weibull scale parameter (characteristic stress), and L_0 a reference gauge length. The cumulative probability of failure, P_F , under a particular stress is given by

$$P_F = \frac{i}{n+1} \quad (3)$$

where i is the number of fibers that have broken at or below a stress level and n is the total number of fibers tested. Rearrangement of the two-parameter Weibull statistical distribution expression (Eq. (2)) gives the following:

$$\ln\left(\ln\left[\frac{1}{1-P_F}\right]\right) = m_f \ln(\sigma_f) - m_f \ln\left(\sigma_0 \left(\frac{L_0}{L}\right)^{\frac{1}{m_f}}\right) \quad (4)$$

Hence the Weibull modulus, m_f can be obtained by linear regression from a Weibull plot of equation (4). Fig.4 shows the Weibull plots of CNTs grown on ultrahigh tensile strength T1000GB PAN-based carbon fibers. The Weibull modulus, m_f , for the CNTs grown on T1000GB fibers were calculated to be 7.2, 10.4, 11.9, respectively [7]. The Weibull modulus, m_f , for the T1000GB fibers with sizing were found to be 5.9, 9.2, 11.9, respectively [3]. The results clearly show that the grafting of CNTs improves the Weibull modulus of carbon fibers at gauge length of 5 and 25 mm, and the Weibull modulus of CNTs grafted carbon fibers at gauge length of 1 mm is almost similar to that in the as-received state.

Fig.4. Weibull plots for CNTs grafted T1000GB PAN-based carbon fibers.

3.4 Tensile strength vs. Weibull modulus

Fig.5 shows the relation between the Weibull modulus, m_f and the average tensile strength, $\sigma_{f,ave}$ of CNTs grown on T1000GB PAN-based carbon fibers.

Fig.5. Relation between the Weibull modulus and the average tensile strength of CNTs grafted T1000GB PAN-based carbon fibers.

The results clearly show that the Weibull modulus increased with increasing the average tensile strength. It is evident that there is a linear relation between the Weibull modulus and the average tensile strength of the CNTs grafted and as-received PAN-based carbon fibers on log-log scale.

A potential mechanism for enhanced tensile strength at longer gauge length is thought to be the three-dimensional network structures of CNTs. Fig.6 shows the schematic model of CNTs-grafted carbon fiber filament.

Fig.6. Schematic model of CNTs-grafted carbon fiber filament.

The growth of the dense CNTs networks on carbon fibers may lead to reduction of the strength-limiting defects and work as a tab. The fracture behaviors of CNTs-grafted carbon fiber at longer gauge length could be seen as that of ungrafted carbon fiber at shorter gauge length, which in turn, improves the tensile strength and Weibull modulus. This result also observed in the tensile strength vs. Weibull modulus relation as shown in Fig.5.

4 Conclusions

- (1) The average tensile strengths of CNTs grown on high strength T1000GB fibers at gauge length of 1, 5 and 25 mm were 8.97, 8.23 and 6.73 GPa. The average tensile strength increased with decreasing the gauge length.
- (2) The grafting of CNTs improves the average tensile strength and the Weibull modulus of high strength T1000GB PAN-based carbon fibers at gauge length of 5 and 25 mm, although the average

tensile strength and the Weibull modulus at gauge length of 1 mm is almost similar to that in the as-received state.

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